

An Introductory Review Of Anomaly Detection Methods In Smart Grids

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Abstract. Cyber Physical systems such as smart grids have the potential to address the future energy crisis. Because of the bidirectional flow of information across various domains in a smart grid, anomaly detection is one of the prime security related challenges. Machine learning models have emerged as one of the prospective artificial intelligence technologies to model supervised and unsupervised data for analysis and prediction. This paper reviews the various anomaly detection schemes in a Smart Grid Infrastructure based on machine learning techniques.

Keywords: Machine learning, Smart Grids, supervised learning, unsupervised learning, Anomaly detection..

1 Introduction

This The Smart Grid (SG) is a distributed power framework that enables the two-way communication of information and energy between the utilities and customers. The infrastructure of the SG encompasses various domains such as bulk generation, distribution, transmission and operations spanning customers and service providers in the energy market [1]. A Smart grid protection system is a subsystem of SG that focuses on protecting the reliability, security and privacy against various anomalies. Anomaly detection involves monitoring the metering, measurement and transmission of energy (and information) leading to identification, localization and prediction of factors leading to failure of a SG. An effective anomaly detection model can successfully bring about reliability, security and privacy of a SG. While government organizations across the world enforce legislations and standards to ensure a safe and reliable SG, technologies like machine learning can actively contribute to the analysis, monitoring and identification of anomalies at various points in a smart grid. Various supervised and unsupervised machine learning based algorithms have been proposed for anomaly detection in SC framework.

In this paper, a broad and discursive survey on the anomaly detection schemes associated with machine learning techniques has been presented. The rest of the paper is organized into the following sections: Section 2 elaborate on the security infrastructure of the SG. Section 3 provides a brief description of the machine learning techniques. Section 4 provides an extensive literature survey on the various machine learning models and schemes for anomaly detection. Section 5 summarizes the conclusion and future directions of research on secure SG.

2 SMART GRID SECURITY INFRASTRUCTURE

An understanding of the various domains in an SG infrastructure is paramount to realize the security and privacy requirements with respect to each entity in the domains. The National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) [have defined seven major domains of SG and the entities in each domain [2]. Figure 1. illustrates the SG domains based on the NIST model. Unlike the conventional power grid, distributed resources such as solar plants and wind turbines also contribute energy to the SG. In [3], Pallotti.et.al defines the CIA triad of SG security and lists the various security practices to achieve information security in SG. Localized generation and transmission power units called Microgrids can be constructed and coupled with the Macrogrid (the traditional grid) when in excess power requirement. Information and energy are generated and transmitted between various entities across domains in SG. Data collected from entities like smart meters, sensors and Phasor Measurement Units is rigorously monitored by means of Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) and Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA) systems facilitate [4].

Fig 1. Smart Grid Domains and their Corresponding Entities

Because the SG data is represented in a compatible, transferable and editable format, these entities also have the potential to become the anomaly hotspots. Vulnerable information such as customer’s smart meter profile, billing history and network configuration can be exploited if not properly safeguarded. These data, generated at various domains in an SG infrastructure may be exploited by adversaries such as hackers, cyber terrorists, industrial competitors, organized criminal elements, disgruntled and poorly trained employees to create

anomalies. Since the SC ultimately aims at delivering uninterrupted and reliable energy, anomaly detection has become one of the paramount security challenges in SC.

3 SMART GRID SECURITY INFRASTRUCTURE

Machine learning is a pervasive and powerful class of algorithms designed to learn from data, acquire key insights to make efficient classifications and predictions that drive intelligent decision making. Machine learning approaches are commonly distinguished as Supervised, unsupervised, Semi-supervised and Reinforcement based learning models. Supervised learning deals with labeled and structured data. Unsupervised learning deals with unlabeled data. Semi-supervised learning deals with labeled and unlabeled data. Reinforcement learning involves an agent learning actions that maximizes the rewards and minimizes the risks. Figure 2. illustrates the common machine learning algorithms under each category.

Fig.2 Common Categories of Machine Learning Algorithms

4 LITERATURE SURVEY ON MACHINE LEARNING (ML) APPROACHES FOR ANOMALY DETECTION IN SMART GRID

With respect to anomaly detection, machine learning algorithms are adaptive in handling real time data and give a better performance in detecting malicious behavioral patterns. This section presents the chronological review on the various anomaly detection methods proposed for a smart grid framework based on the various parameters of the energy data.

Kher et.al.in [5][6] proposed a sensor network-based hybrid framework for SG monitoring. The two-layer mesh topology routing protocol consists of local clusters with fixed number of heads at lower level and cluster heads at each node form a linear chain at the upper level. The nodes are synched with the help of neighbor ID. The cluster head controls the various states of the node. Over The Air Programming (OTAP) network deployment is suggested to enable automatic software updation thereby reducing maintenance costs. The data collected from multiple sensors (acceleration, motion, temperature, infrared, vibration) in each node are aggregated and analyzed using a Decision Tree Classifier (J48). The classifier identifies the intrusion values from the normal values. The classification rate using J48 classifier was better than *ZeroR*, *DecisionTable*, *RandomForest* and *ADTree*. The authors claim that the continuous monitoring of the data collected at multiple sensors installed at each node results in a better prediction model.

An embedded anomaly detector was proposed by Raciti et. al [7]. An embedded anomaly detection model periodically collects both the cyber domain data (packet header, connections) and the physical data (energy measurements) and a feature vector is generated. BIRCH inspired incremental clustering algorithm [8] processes the feature vector based on the centroid distance threshold and the number of clusters to determine if it falls under a closest cluster. Several types of attack like data manipulation, recalibration, reset and sleep mode were detected with the algorithm.

In [9], PMU measurements from synchrophasors were analyzed by various classifiers like Naïve Bayes, OneR, NNge, JRipper, Random Forests and Adaboost and evaluated for Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) to identify power System disturbances (both natural and malicious) in a smart grid. The classifiers were tested against three classification schemes based on the event occurrence: multiclass, three-class (attack/natural/no event) and binary (attack/natural). The performance evaluation showed that Random Forests, JRipper and Adaboost combined with JRipper exhibited high precision, OneR and Naïve Bayes exhibited average recall, JRipper and Adaboost combined with JRipper exhibited average recall and JRipper combined with Adaboost exhibited high F-measure. The overall performance evaluation indicated that JRipper combined with Adaboost, a coupling of a tree-based rule generation and a learning ensemble approach is the optimal classifier for a three-class classification scheme.

Ford et.al. [10] proposed an ANN based Intrusion Detection System (IDS) to predict the consumption behavior of the customer. The consumer's energy consumption behavior (ECB) profile included parameters like time and week in addition to the energy consumption data. This data is used to model the customer's consumption behavior using a neural network. The statistical analysis of the predicted value from the neural network compared with the real values helps to identify deviations.

Krishna et.al [11][12] [13] have extensively worked on anomaly detection with respect to meter frauds. In [11] ARIMA forecasting was evaluated and an integrated attack model was defined for detection anomalies in consumption data. In [13] a framework based on Kullback-Leibler Divergence (KLD) was proposed to detect the attack model. The authors have identified 5 classes of attacks and used the KLD to identify meter frauds such as multiple reading from the customer's tariff data. In [12], the authors proposed an anomaly detection based on Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to effectively monitor consumption readings.

The work in [13] is extended in [14] to evaluate signal processing-based detection approaches for meter frauds in alternate resources like solar and wind grid data.

In [15] Rossi et.al focused on detecting collective and contextual anomalies from a stream of smart meter event occurrences. In this paper, association rule mining is used to identify sets of recurrent events instances (frequent itemsets). The most frequent itemsets are extracted by applying an Apriori algorithm. These itemsets are augmented with contextual information. A categorical clustering based on entropy minimization to create clusters of similar categories of features. A clustering silhouette concept is used to identify the best fit of an itemset in an existing cluster. The authors were the first to propose the possibility of a collective and conceptual anomaly detection scheme.

Valdes et.al. [16] analyzed energy measurement samples to identify new data and similar patterns and by combining the concepts of adaptive resonance theory and self-organizing maps. In [17], both supervised and unsupervised machine learning techniques were used to identify stealth false data injection in a state estimation. PCA is used for dimensionality reduction and a distributed SVM is applied to distinguish a stealth attack from a normal attack. Ge.et.al [18] studied the performance of ANN on smart meter data such as line voltage and power load to detect load altering in the power grid. In [19], an Intrusion Detection System (IDS) was installed with sensors in all the network components (HAN, NAN and WAN). Data from the sensors in each of the network was preprocessed and tested on 20 classifiers. Five classifiers provided better precision: J48, JRip, BayesNet, SVM and MLP. J48 classifier showed the highest precision discovering all types of attack.

An IDS for the AMI architecture to protect data collected from devices like smart meter and AMI headend was proposed in [20] using CART decision tree because of its ability to perform both classification and regression. The network flow features are extracted from the traffic and decision tree is generated based on the CART algorithm. Chamie et.al [21] used the real time data from the μ PMUs to identify transients caused by manipulating the electric devices (circuit breakers and switches). The proposed anomaly detection, Pseudo-Supervised Learning (PSL) algorithm is a two-step process that initially employs Isolation Forests, an unsupervised learning to capture the normal data features (termed as "pseudo label") followed by non-linear regression, a supervised learning on the pseudo label to learn a model that best fits the features to the pseudo label. Thus, this approach can identify the anomaly features that are not part of a normal pattern.

Zhang et.al [22] proposed a semi-supervised Generative Gaussian mixture model (GMM) for analyzing the customer's energy consumption data (from AMI infrastructure) to detect energy theft. The GMM model is used to generate the threshold from the customer's previous consumption (non-malicious) data. The thresholds are compared with the new data to detect anomalous behaviours. An ensemble learning model that combines the results from multiple decision trees was proposed in [23] for a Transactive Energy Systems (TES). TES is an essential part of the smart grid that monitors the information transactions between various stakeholders in the grid to make decisions on energy consumption and demand response. The proposed ensemble approach combines the predictions called "confidence" from 10 decision tree models based on various controllers to generate a combiner measure called "plurality" to boost the overall performance.

Ayad et.al [24] investigated Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) to detect False Data Injection (FDI) attacks in a smart grid. In RNN, the memory created with the information from previous outputs thereby storing sequential time information as state. This state information is used to predict the new state (output). The authors were the first to consider RNN as a tool for anomaly detection in smart grid. Schuster et.al. [25] proposed a self-learning network anomaly detection for a real-time energy network. The detector is trained with normal and anomalous traffic traces using six major classifiers. In [26], machine learning algorithms like Principal components analysis (PCA), Competitive Neural Network Learning (CNL) and other statistical methods were used to analyze syslog data in a real-time smart grid to establish trust metrics between substations. Lore et.al. [27] proposed a server-centric anomaly detection framework that utilizes the correlation between spatial and temporal data from multi modal solar farms. The models were analyzed using Classification algorithms like vector autoregressive models (VAR), deep neural networks (DNN), long short-term memory networks (LSTM), inverse PCA reconstruction (iPCA) and deep auto-encoders (DAE) and evaluated for replay, correlation, delay, scaling and random attacks.

Ouyang et.al [28] extracted the time series features from power consumption data collected from IoT device in the grid. The extracted summary, transform and shift features are trained using multi-view learning model and stacking is applied. Pereira et.al [29] proposed a variational recurrent autoencoder and a variational selfattention mechanism (VSAM) based anomaly detection on time series data of a solar grid. Anomalous patterns are detected by using the probabilistic reconstruction metrics as anomaly scores. Yeckle et.al [30] explored the performance of seven outlier algorithms (Local Outlier Factor (LOF), Local Density Factor (LDF), Flexible Kernel Density Estimates (KDEOS), Influenced Outlierness (INFLO), Relative Density-based Outlier Score (RDOS), Mutual k-nearest neighbor (MNN) and Indegree Number (ODIN)) on AMI data preprocessed using k-means clustering achieving feature reduction. INFLO and RDOS outliers showed better performance. Veloso et.al [31] proposed the implementation of Cognitive Smart Plugs (SPs) for visualization and monitoring of residential area energy data using machine learning. The Electric Load Signature (ELS) generated from each SP (or SM) in a grid is filtered and identified using Decision Tree and Naïve Bayes learning algorithms.

Cui et.al [32] developed a machine learning anomaly detection methodology that combines k means clustering (unsupervised), Naïve Bayes (supervised) and dynamic programming to detect cyberattacks for load forecasting data. Buzau et.al [33] proposed the implementation of XGBoost Classifier on smart meter data such as EC, alarms and electrical magnitudes to detect the anomalies caused by non-technical losses such as installation error, meter parameterization error and faulty meter. Fenza et.al [34] proposed a context aware framework to detect anomalies in identifying energy consumption profiles (concept drift) by training a Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) model on profiles clustered using k-means clustering. In [35], an anomaly detection system based on feature grouping combined with linear correlation coefficient (FGLCC) algorithm is proposed where the ID3 classifier is used for decision making. Marino et.al [36] proposed a cyber-physical sensor (IREST) for detecting anomalies where unsupervised (One Class SVM) and supervised (Decision Trees and Random forests) learning models were used. In [37], Logistic Regression Analysis is implemented data from Synchronphasor systems, like Phasor Measurement Units (PMUs) for anomaly detection.

Roy [38] explored four classifiers: Random Forests, Naïve Bayes, XGBoost and SVM to implement network intrusion detection on highly unbalanced data. XGBoost and Random Forest showed better performance. Soleymani et.al [39] proposed unsupervised clustering-based approach and uses a correlation based stochastic method to locate the anomaly provenances that cause outage and energy theft. Trevizan et.al [40] proposed anomaly detection using Reed-Xaoli (RX) algorithm and a Chi-squared test for the detection FDI attacks in power system measurements. Deep learning techniques like deep auto-encoders were implemented in the distributed grid network [41] to address PMU data manipulation attacks. In [42] the unsupervised learning model was proposed based on GMM-LDA clustering for feature learning and PSO-SVM on smart meter data from AMI to trace abnormal power consumption. The integrated learning model performed better than the supervised SVM learning. Shafee et.al [43] proposes a deep recurrent neural network based anomaly detector learning model to detect Electric Vehicles (EVs) reporting false state of change values in a smart grid. A Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm was used to perform an exhaustive grid search.

Sahu et.al [44] compared Logistic regression and artificial neural network (ANN) classification models on IoT networks and concluded ANN showed better precision. Shereen et.al [45] proposed two threshold-based and two machine detectors for monitoring time variables from the PMU clock system. The data-driven detectors were unsupervised Auto-Encoder Neural Network Detector and supervised Random Forest detector. However, the performance of threshold detectors was optimal compared to the machine learning detectors. Ravikumar et.al [46] explored seven supervised learning models for classification and mitigation technique for anomaly detection in wide-area damping control (WADC). Barua et.al [47] proposed a neuro cognitive-inspired unsupervised learning model called Hierarchical Temporal Memory (HTM) to detect spatial and temporal anomalies in μ PMU data. In [48], bidirectional RNN based anomaly detection was proposed for IEEE 1815.1-based network. The proposed system was effective for CPS malware behavior (CMB), false data injection (FDI), and disabling reassembly (DR) attacks.

Ma et.al [49] proposed a One Class SVM based anomaly detection to identify outliers in large scale energy data. In [50] One R, Random Forest, Naive Bayes and JRipper models were analyzed on a three class dataset for anomaly detection. Random Forest classifier exhibited highest detection rate. In [51], deep learning based anomaly detection and classification system were proposed by combining Autoencoder and Generative Adversarial Network (GAN). Ahmed et.al [52] proposed a distributed deep autoencoder based anomaly detection over PMU data streams. Khaledian et.al [53] combined three unsupervised classifiers for anomaly detection and classification on PMU time series data. The authors applied a kalman filter algorithm to condition the synchrophasor data.

4.1 Inferences from the Literature Survey:

The following points are inferred as a result of the above survey:

- Machine learning algorithms are highly utilized by anomaly detection systems because of the ability to acquire useful insights from historical data and make useful predictions. The outliers were able to mitigate most of the attacks caused in a smart grid.

- Machine learning algorithms approaches can be implemented on any type of framework to train and test the detection rate of the anomalies.
- The Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI) from the operations domain and Phasor Measurement Units (PMU) from the transmission domain are pivotal centers that generate grid data. Machine learning models are trained for data generated from both AMI and PMU.
- Deep learning models are ideal for the future smart grid anomaly detection systems as huge data with minimum human intervention can be monitored and trained.

5. Conclusion and Future Directions of Research

Smart grid infrastructure has the capacity to accommodate distributed energy resources to meet the rising energy crisis. However, the dynamic and bidirectional nature of the data in the grid makes anomalies inevitable incurring huge losses. Machine learning algorithms are progressive in the design of effective anomaly detection framework. In this paper, a chronological survey of the various machine learning approaches for anomaly detection in smart grids is presented. The survey reveals that multiple machine learning techniques are experimented against any proposed framework to analyze the anomaly detection rate. It is also seen that deep learning techniques are the future direction of research for the design of a secure smart grid.

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